

THERAPEUTIC ROLE OF NEROBHI PLUS OIL IN PAIN AND INFLAMMATION: CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Pain is an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience that can negatively impact daily functioning. Modern and unhealthy lifestyles result this uncomfortable state, which can be managed by the most common practice of choosing painkillers. Although they do relieve pain, the side effects are in many cases more concerning than the original condition. Ayurveda provide a more holistic approach to dealing with pain and related symptoms such as inflammation and stiffness that appear in classical texts. There is an abundant list of *Aushadhi dravyas* mentioned in Ayurvedic texts to assist with pain and related health conditions. These *Aushadhi dravyas* are used to create formulations that sustain healthy state of body. Nerobhiplus oil is an Ayurvedic formulation made from five *Aushadhi dravyas*, which includes *Sarson* oil, *Haldi*, *Dalchini*, *Shunthi* and *Chuna*. This formulation addresses pain and inflammation quickly by reducing the aggravation of *Vata Dosha*. This *Dosha* responds to most pain and inflammation complaints as experienced in the human body. This formulation pacifies aggravated *Dosha* along

with reducing pain and inflammation. This formulation has been shown to relieve muscle and joint pain without complications or fewer side effects. Present article demonstrated a case report showing therapeutic role of Nerobhi Plus Oil in the management of pain and inflammation.

KEYWORDS: *Nerobhi Plus oil, Vata Dosha, Pain, Inflammation, Shoola.*

INTRODUCTION

Pain is the primary symptom that impacts a person's quality of life. There have been several strong analgesics used to manage acute or chronic pain. Nevertheless, the use of higher doses of these medications poses numerous side-effects that could lead to respiratory complications, vomiting, nausea and psychological dependence, etc. Chronic pain has a completely different process of management by using Ayurvedic traditional cases. Pain is co-related to *Shoola* in Ayurveda, which involves pathological events of aggravated *Vata Dosha*. There are many herbal drugs which help to relieve pain and inflammation. Nerobhi Plus oil, is natural formulation made with these herbal drugs (*Aushadh Dravya*) that comply with the body's natural capabilities to heal without adverse effects.

Nerobhi Plus oil works by pacifying and normalizing vitiated *Vata dosha*, relieves muscle or joint pain, cures *Vata Nanatmaja Vikara* and reduces symptoms of inflammation such as stiffness and numbness, etc. This case study demonstrated role of Nerobhi Plus oil as analgesic and anti-inflammatory medicines.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The selected drug formulation (Nerobhi Plus oil) procured from Manojivan Pharmaceuticals, Kota, Rajasthan, India. This oil was formulated by *Siddha* preparation process of ancient Ayurveda; contents of formulation are as follows:

- ✓ *Sarson Oil*: 100 ml
- ✓ *Dalchini Twak*: 45 g
- ✓ *Haldi*: 25 g Bulb
- ✓ *Chuna*: 6 g powder
- ✓ *Shunthi Panchanga*: 25 g Bulb

Ayurvedic and pharmacological properties of contents of Nerobhi Plus oil formulation:

- ✓ *Sarson Oil*, belonging to the family *Cruciferae*, is categorized under *Kandughana* and *Pippalyadi Varga*. The seeds are used for their *Vatahara*, *Krimighna*, *Medoghna* and *Kaphashamaka* actions. Chemically, it contains rutin and arabinogalacton and acts as an antihelminthic and rubefacient agent.
- ✓ *Dalchini* (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum*) is belong from the *Lauraceae* family, found in the *Eladi* and *Karpuradi Varga*, utilizes its bark, stem, and oil for *Vishapaha*, *Krumighna*,

Pittala, and *Kantashuddhikara* properties. It contains cinnamaldehyde and phellandrene, exhibiting antimicrobial, wound healing, and immunity-enhancing effects.

- ✓ *Haldi* from the *Zingiberaceae* family, listed in the *Lekhaniya* and *Kushthaghna* groups, uses its rhizome for *Vranahara*, *Vishaghna*, *Krimighna*, and *Pittarechaka* actions. Curcumin and β -sitosterol are its main constituents, providing antioxidant, antidiabetic, and hepatoprotective activity.
- ✓ *Chuna* (Calcium Carbonate), known as *Khatika*, is described in *Rasatarangini* and Ayurveda *Prakash* as *Shishira*, *Tikta-Madhura*, *Shothanashini*, and *Kaphadahahara*, exhibiting anti-inflammatory and cooling properties.
- ✓ *Shunthi* (*Zingiber officinale*) from the *Scitamineae* family, grouped under *Pippalyadi Varga*, uses its rhizome for *Dipaniya*, *Aamavataghna*, and *Shothahara* actions. Containing curcumin and citral, it serves as a rubefacient, stimulant, and digestive agent.

Collectively, above mentioned drugs exhibit synergistic anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial and *Vata-Kapha* pacifying effects. Their *Dosha Karma* and Ayurvedic attributes are presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1: *Dosha Karma* and Ayurvedic attributes of contents of Nerobhi Plus oil formulation.

Drug	Rasa	Guna	Veerya	Vipaka	Dosha Karma
<i>Sarson Tail</i> (<i>Mustard Oil</i>)	Pungent (<i>Katu</i>)	Light (<i>Laghu</i>), Hot and Sharp (<i>Ushna</i> , <i>Tikshna</i>)	Hot (<i>Ushna</i>)	Pungent (<i>Katu</i>)	<i>Deepana</i> , <i>Lekhana</i> , pacifies <i>Vata</i> and <i>Kapha</i>
<i>Haldi</i> (<i>Turmeric</i>)	Bitter and Pungent (<i>Tikta</i> , <i>Katu</i>)	Dry and Light (<i>Ruksha</i> , <i>Laghu</i>)	Hot (<i>Ushna</i>)	Pungent (<i>Katu</i>)	Pacifies <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Pitta</i> ; improves complexion and skin disorders
<i>Dalchini</i> (<i>Cinnamon</i>)	Pungent, Bitter, and Sweet (<i>Katu</i> , <i>Tikta</i> , <i>Madhura</i>)	Light, Dry, and Sharp (<i>Laghu</i> , <i>Ruksha</i> , <i>Tikshna</i>)	Hot (<i>Ushna</i>)	Pungent (<i>Katu</i>)	Increases <i>Vata</i> and <i>Kapha</i>
<i>Shunthi</i> (<i>Dry Ginger</i>)	Pungent (<i>Katu</i>)	Heavy, Dry, and Sharp (<i>Guru</i> , <i>Ruksha</i> , <i>Tikshna</i>)	Hot (<i>Ushna</i>)	Sweet (<i>Madhura</i>)	Pacifies <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Vata</i>
<i>Khatika</i> (<i>Chuna</i> / <i>Calcium</i> <i>Carbonate</i>)	Sweet and Bitter (<i>Madhura</i> , <i>Tikta</i>)	Cold (<i>Shita</i>)	Cold (<i>Shita</i>)	—	Pacifies <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Pitta</i> , relieves burning sensation (<i>Dahahara</i>)

CASE REPORT

A 54-year-old female from Sogariya, Rajasthan, presented with pain in the knees, lower back, and ankle joints, accompanied by inflammation in the knee joints and numbness in the legs and feet persisting for the past two months. Based on the clinical findings, the condition was diagnosed as *Shoola*, indicating pain associated with inflammatory conditions.

TREATMENT PROTOCOL

Nerobhi Plus Oil was prescribed along with a suitable diet chart. About 5–10 ml of Nerobhi Plus Oil was applied twice daily for seven days for *Abhyanga* using the fingertips and palms. The patient was advised to continue *Mridu Abhyanga* at home along with conservative medication.

- ✓ *Pathya* (Wholesome Diet) suggested; *Shashti Shali*, *Laghu Ahara*, *Draksha* and green leafy vegetables.
- ✓ *Apathya* (Unwholesome Diet) which are to be avoided; fried and oily food, sour substances, *Guru* and excessively greasy food items.

Suggested Precautions and Safety Measures

1. Avoided prolonged walking and running.
2. Refrain from weight lifting.
3. Avoided bending or performing heavy exercises.
4. Use a support tube while sitting.
5. Climb stairs in a backward position to reduce joint strain.

Assessment Scales/Scoring Pattern

Assessment Scale	Score	Description
<i>Pain Scale</i>	0	No pain
	1	Mild pain
	2	Moderate pain
	3	Severe pain
	4	Unbearable pain
<i>Efficacy Scale</i>	0	Poor
	1	Moderate
	2	Good
	3	Excellent
<i>Tolerability Scale</i>	0	Poor
	1	Moderate
	2	Good
	3	Excellent

RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

There was a significant difference in pain & associated symptoms after the completion of therapy, the major outcomes observed as follows:

- ✓ Patient was able to walk without any difficulty.
- ✓ No complaints of pain & no visible inflammations were observed.
- ✓ Patient was able to move to normal flexion & extension.
- ✓ No adverse side effects were observed.
- ✓ No signs of stiffness and numbness.

By the time of the first follow-up (**Table 2**), pain, stiffness, and tenderness steadily decreased to the extent that the patient reported a complete (100%) alleviation of all symptoms (**Figure 1**). Both the efficacy and tolerability started to improve from the commencement of treatment to the follow-up. The efficacy began at a level of zero and reached its maximum (+100%), while the tolerability showed a profound increase of +500% indicating an excellent level of acceptance and adaptability to the therapy by the patient.

Table 2: Improvement in Assessment Parameters.

Symptoms	Before Treatment	After Therapy	First Follow-up
Pain (VAS scale)	3	2	0
Stiffness	Grade 2	0	0
Tenderness	Grade 2	0	0
Efficacy	0	2	3
Tolerability	0-1	2	3

Figure 1: Effect of therapy on assessment parameters before and after treatment.

DISCUSSIO

This research project was an examination of a traditional Ayurvedic method for managing chronic pain and inflammation in the lower back, buttocks, knee joints and legs through its application of the product Nerobhi Plus oil. Even though the results are very preliminary and based on just one patient, the results are promising and there were no negative side effects noted. The formulation contained ingredients such as *Sarson* oil, *Dalchini*, *Haldi*, *Chuna* and *Shunthi*, which are known for their anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties and can be applied in *Abhyanga* form. These ingredients served to decrease pain and inflammation when applied locally through *Abhyanga*.

Probable mode of actions of prescribes formulation

Mustard Oil contains anti-inflammatory compounds that improve blood circulation, reduce stiffness, and provide warmth and relief to painful and inflamed areas. *Dalchini* reduces systemic inflammation, cramps, and pain while minimizing oxidative stress. *Haldi* acts similarly to NSAIDs with antioxidant properties; prevents cell damage and modulates inflammatory pathways. *Shunthi* alleviates pain by pacifying *Vata Dosha*, reducing *Ama*, stimulating digestive fire and support in detoxification process. *Chuna* reduces external inflammation and promotes wound healing.

CONCLUSION

From the results, it can be concluded that the Ayurvedic formulation Nerobhi Plus oil is very effective in reducing pain, stiffness and inflammation, etc. A progressive decline in pain was observed within seven days of treatment, and patients reported no difficulty in walking. Additionally, no adverse effects were noted during the study period. The outcomes highlight the classical and holistic benefits of Nerobhi Plus oil, demonstrating significant relief from pain and inflammation.

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